

Navigating the Crossroads: Intersectionality in Engaged Scholarship Among Black Female Academics in South African Universities

Dr. Tandiwe Mdlungu

University of South Africa (UNISA)

ABSTRACT

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In South Africa, where women make up more than half of the population but are still underrepresented in higher education. Within engaged scholarship initiatives, black female academics encounter intersecting challenges that are shaped by factors such as gender, race, class, and other aspects of identity. These difficulties are exacerbated by the prevalence of Gender-Based Violence (GBV) and overlapping roles, such as caring for the home and providing care for others. Furthermore, in South African universities women are regarded as a niche area in the academic community. The study aims to explore how different sides of identity interact and influence experiences in academic engagement, highlighting the challenges and possibilities Black women face in higher education. To obtain insights from Black female academics in South African universities, this study used a qualitative research methodology. The results highlight the complex interactions between intersectional identities in Black female academics' engaged scholarship initiatives. Findings further reveal the difficulties they encounter, such as managing their academic obligations with caregiving and household duties and their academic goals. The study also emphasizes how marginalized women's studies programs are in South African universities, which speaks to larger concerns about the acceptance and validation of women's voices and viewpoints in higher education. The study recommends the creation of a more equitable and inclusive academic environment for Black female academics in South Africa based on the findings. Among these are, putting in place programs and policies to assist work-life balance and cater to the unique needs of Black women in higher education, boosting the integration of gender perspectives across disciplines, and increasing the visibility and acknowledgment of women's studies programs in South African universities, and supplying Black female academics with mentors and support systems to help them overcome intersectional obstacles and progress in their academic careers.

KEYWORDS:

Academia, Black Females, Education, Engaged Scholarship, Intersectionality

BACKGROUND OF THE STUDY

Women in South Africa are still underrepresented in higher education, particularly in positions of academic leadership and research, while making up more than half of the population in South Africa (Collins, 2022). Due to their intersecting identities of gender, ethnicity, and class, female scholars face additional challenges, making this lack of representation more apparent. The fact that only 5% of Black Africans between the ages of 18 and 29 were enrolled in colleges or universities as of 2022, according to recent data,

Corresponding Author: Dr. Tandiwe Mdlungu

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highlights the severe obstacles to enrolment and advancement in the educational system. In addition, the Gender Parity Index (GPI) for South African education was 1.41 in 2022, indicating a bias towards female admittance. However, this does not always result in representation in academic roles. Black female scholars commonly face hurdles such as lack of backing, and underrepresentation of gender-related studies. These obstacles impede their involvement in engaged scholarship. Moreover, Apartheid's lingering consequences and systematic injustices provide difficulties for Black women academics. The barriers we encounter are deeply embedded in racial and economic divisions, as well as systems of power and privilege that reinforce gender norms. These barriers stand in the way of advancement and job stability (Mkhize & Sillah, 2023). Black women, in the setting encounter forms of discrimination that stem from their diverse backgrounds and

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experiences. In addition to socioeconomic difficulties, they encounter racial and gender bias, as well as linguistic and cultural impediments, adding to their academic difficulties. In addition to these challenges, women from marginalized communities are disproportionately affected by gender-based violence (GBV), the low representation of women in STEM fields, and the unequal distribution of caregiving and household responsibilities (Maseko, 2022). Black women scholars have fewer opportunities to actively participate in the academic environment and their professional advancement is impeded by systemic impediments.

Instead of being acknowledged as important members of the academic community, Black women academics are often marginalized and classified as a specialized group in colleges (Bagilhole, 2017). This marginalization is demonstrated by differences in the availability of resources, a lack of mentorship possibilities, and the fact that their work frequently goes unnoticed in settings. Cultures that do not value involvement in engaged scholarship, a research approach that seeks to bridge the gap between academia and the community, exacerbate the marginalization even though it has the potential to address significant societal issues and improve higher education (Collins, 2022).

In the context of the situation described above this research aims to explore how Black women academics in universities in South Africa are managing their involvement in Engage scholarship while also dealing with the complexities of their various intersected identities. By undertaking this study and highlighting these insights about academic experiences in South African universities within engaged scholarship programs the study's objective is to support the push for fairer and more inclusive approaches to teaching and learning practices in the country's academic field.

RESEARCH QUESTIONS

- RQ 1: how do Black female academics in South African universities manage the opportunities and difficulties brought about by their intersectional identities?
- RQ 2: How do institutional culture and societal expectations, among other systemic barriers, affect Black female scholars' academic engagement and career paths in South Africa?

LITERATURE REVIEW

Women, especially Black female academics, encounter systemic obstacles when navigating academia, according to studies on gender and higher education in South Africa (Bawa & Francis, 2021; Singh, 2022). The colonial and apartheid legacies that have left behind structural inequalities that disproportionately affect women from historically marginalized communities are deeply ingrained in the South African higher education system. Disparities in research funding, underrepresentation in senior academic positions,

and restricted access to professional development opportunities are just a few examples of how these obstacles appear. This institutional marginalization is a reflection of larger social trends in which views of women's roles within and outside of academia are still shaped by patriarchal norms (Mabokela, 2020).

Academic Inequality and Gender

Gender inequality in academia is a persistent problem on a global scale. Studies from nations like the US, UK, and Australia have shown that it is extremely difficult for female academics to catch up to their male counterparts, especially in fields like STEM that are dominated by men. These challenges include the "double burden" of juggling work and home obligations, a lack of mentorship, and unconscious bias in hiring and promotion (Morley, 2018; O'Connor, 2020). The fact that structural barriers still exist despite progress in gender equity policies emphasizes the significance of systemic change as opposed to piecemeal solutions.

These difficulties are exacerbated in developing regions, like sub-Saharan Africa, by sociocultural elements and resource limitations. Research on Nigerian universities, for instance, shows that institutional cultures are firmly rooted in patriarchal views, which marginalizes female academics and their scholarship (Adedokun, 2021). According to research, female academics in Kenya are frequently restricted to teaching-heavy positions and have little access to leadership or research opportunities (Mwangi & Orodho, 2019). These instances are relevant to South Africa, where women especially Black women frequently hold vulnerable academic positions.

The intertwining dynamics of race and class in South Africa further exacerbate gender inequality in higher education. Black female academics face particular difficulties, including tokenism, overt and covert racism, and the expectation that they must put in more work for institutional diversity initiatives without receiving the same acknowledgement or assistance (Pillay, 2022). This phenomenon is consistent with the intersectionality theory of Crenshaw (1991), which holds that oppressive systems are interconnected and cannot be studied separately.

The absence of institutional support for research focusing on racial and gender equity is a major problem in South African academia. For example, feminist scholarship and women's studies programs are frequently marginalized and underappreciated, pushed to the outside of institutional priorities (Potgieter & Moleko, 2023). This devaluation is a reflection of larger patriarchal trends in academia, as fields deemed "feminine" or "non-essential" are routinely disregarded in favor of those that are in accordance with demands from the market.

The difficulties experienced by women in academics are made worse by the pervasiveness of gender-based violence (GBV) in South African society. In addition to having

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significant psychological and emotional effects, GBV interferes with women's career paths and prevents them from completely embracing their academic responsibilities (Sibanda, 2023). Numerous institutions have come under fire for their poor reactions to GBV, with many failing to establish secure and encouraging settings for both female students and academics.

The Role of Academic Black Women

Black women scholars in South Africa have shown incredible agency and resiliency in the face of these obstacles. Through their scholarship, they have addressed social inequalities impacting underrepresented populations and contributed to transformative work in addition to advancing academic understanding (Fataar & Bitzer, 2019). This includes studies on topics like gender-based violence, poverty, and educational access, as well as initiatives to challenge Eurocentric academic paradigms and decolonize curriculum. Similar resilience characteristics among academically marginalized women are visible on a global scale. For instance, Black women academics in the US have created crucial frameworks for comprehending and resolving systematic injustices by pioneering disciplines like intersectionality and Black feminist theory (Collins, 2000). Despite structural marginalization, these contributions demonstrate the promise of engaged scholarship as a weapon for social change and empowerment.

While the experiences of South African women academics are similar to those of women around the world, comparative analysis shows that the socioeconomic realities and historical legacies of the nation intensify and complicate these difficulties. For example, while women around the world struggle with the "leaky pipeline" phenomenon the loss of women at every academic level Black women in South Africa experience a higher attrition rate in academic settings due to the interaction of race, gender, and class. This emphasizes the necessity of context-specific, locally tailored initiatives that take into account the particularities of South African academics while referencing international best practices.

THEORETICAL FOUNDATION

To better understand how many social identities, such as gender and race, interact to produce experiences of advantage and disadvantage, Kimberlé Crenshaw introduced the concept of intersectionality in 1989, which serves as the foundation for this study. The study focuses on Black women scholars in South Africa and shows how colonial and apartheid-era injustices impact environments and social mores in this country. The intersectional framework emphasizes that rather than focusing on each identity separately, it is crucial to take into account the interrelated effects of marginalization and discrimination (Mamas, 2021). This method makes it possible to examine the intricate

difficulties that Black women face at South African universities.

In South Africa's academic environment, women frequently experience multiple forms of discrimination simultaneously. As Mama (2021) points out, these include racism that minimizes their accomplishments, gender prejudices that increase caregiving duties and social demands on them, and economic disparities that limit women access to resources and opportunity for professional advancement. In South Africa, the academic community has historically been shaped by patriarchal norms, which makes it inhospitable to scholars who challenge these standards through their identities. observing the circumstances. This study will examine how these characteristics affect the advancement and success of American women scholars in academic contexts, taking into account a variety of aspects and perspectives.

This research does not examine intersectionality. Additionally, it makes use of engaged scholarship as a framework to bridge the gap between academic research and real-world impact. When there are systematic inequalities and colleges need to have a significant impact on change, engaged scholarship becomes essential. Engaged scholarship emphasizes the need of collaborating with communities to effectively address problems and advancing research that is inclusive of a range of viewpoints and responsive to societal demands, as noted by Bozalek and Leibowitz (2019). This approach enables Black women researchers to demonstrate their independence in the classroom by relating their research to their experiences and commitment to equity.

Engaged scholarship challenges the hierarchical nature of academic knowledge creation and allows underrepresented scholars to reshape academia's relationship with society. It also reinterprets learning boundaries in a more inclusive way, values diversity and equity, and prioritizes collaborative knowledge building. Of particular note is the important contributions made by Black women academics to the transformation of academia and society at large.

By integrating intersectionality and active research engagement in academia and social problems, this conceptual model provides insight into how Black women scholars in South African universities handle their roles as educators and change agents. This highlights their ability to take action and the significant impact of their contributions, while also acknowledging the challenges they face. The study aims to improve conversations about equity, inclusivity, and social justice in the field of education by looking at this viewpoint.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

To achieve the objective of this study, a qualitative research methodology was adopted. Through secondary data analysis, this study focused on investigating the experiences of female academics in South Africa. According to Saunders et al. (2019), secondary data analysis involves using pre-existing

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data, such as published papers and institutional reports, to investigate new research questions or points of view.

By doing this, researchers were able to use a variety of resources to identify patterns, problems, and opportunities related to the intersections of gender, racism, and class in academic settings.

The study made use of several documents and articles.

1. Research papers and chapters from many sources have shown the opportunities and obstacles faced by Black female scholars in various systems. The interplay of identities, bias, and gender inequity are among the subjects they examine.
2. Research from academic institutions and governmental organizations was examined. The papers examined statistics on racial and gender diversity in academia, as well as policies and initiatives aimed at fostering diversity and inclusivity.
3. Media and Press coverage examined the debates surrounding the barriers faced by women in academics by reviewing articles and opinions from well-known African media outlets, such as the Sunday Times and Mail & Guardian. The material regularly included examples and concerns on how prejudice and social norms affect Black female academics.
4. Women researchers' stories of professional struggles and solutions to systemic obstacles were presented at academic conferences and panels.
5. works of autobiography that have been published.
6. Reflections from female researchers on the difficulties of balancing work obligations and personal responsibilities were shared in blogs, interviews, and first-hand narratives.

Articles and documents were chosen for several reasons. Secondary sources provided a variety of perspectives and views from other fields, which made it easier to thoroughly examine the intricate challenges faced by Black women researchers.

A lot of articles were authored by academics or featured their viewpoints, which offered authentic answers to their daily experiences. Because secondary data sources were readily available for the study endeavour, data could be gathered without the challenges of primary data collection, such as conducting surveys or interviews.

Analyzing Secondary Articles

For data analysis coding was used in the research to properly assess the papers. The primary steps involved were the selection of articles based on their applicability to the topics of gender, racism, class, and academic involvement in the study. The selection criteria considered the reliability of the sources and the recentness of the publication. Information was arranged the papers' sections based on their core themes, such as intersectional scholarship and structural barriers. The data was arranged during the research study's analysis and theme identification phases to identify recurring themes and subjects of interest.

The topics were examined using the intersectionality theory viewpoint to demonstrate how different types of discrimination interact to impact the challenges. Incorporating articles into the study allowed it to build upon and integrate previously published data while offering a perspective on the relationship between identity and active engagement in education. The study explored the aspects using a range of sources. Black women researchers' educational paths in South Africa are impacted by structural arrangements, cultural influences, and individual characteristics. The research's thoroughness was not enhanced by this methodology. Additionally, it ensured that the participants' perspectives and narratives were situated within the broader institutional and societal frameworks.

In order to ensure that the findings are reliable and credible, the research employed triangulation techniques, which combined data sources like documents and media with interviews to lessen bias and enhance the analysis in-depth. To capture the actual experiences of Black women academics in South Africa and make sure that the findings appropriately represented their lives, the research provided detailed narratives that were rich in context. By employing this framework, the research endeavour adds to the discourse on equity and diversity in educational establishments by offering significant insights into how institutional processes

FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

The document's analysis revealed themes that revealed the challenges and opportunities faced by Black women academics working on university-engaged scholarship in South Africa. These subjects, which are founded on the intersection of racial, gender, and class issues, provide insight into the institutional barriers that affect their paths. .

Theme	Description
1. Balancing Academic Work and Caregiving Responsibilities	Highlights the challenges Black female academics face in balancing academic duties with caregiving responsibilities, often due to inadequate support systems.
2. Marginalization of Gender Studies and Feminist Research	Gender and feminist research is often sidelined, receiving less recognition, funding, and institutional support compared to male-dominated disciplines.

3. Institutional Barriers	Institutional culture and policies do not adequately support Black female academics, highlighting a need for equitable workload, mentorship, and leadership opportunities.
4. Resilience and Collective Agency	Despite challenges, Black female academics use engaged scholarship to validate marginalized voices, create social impact, and connect academia with community needs.
5. Engaged Scholarship as a Tool for Social Change	Emphasizes the formation of support networks and alliances among Black female academics to share knowledge, provide emotional support, and advocate for change.

Balancing Academic Work and Caregiving Responsibilities

The results frequently address the balancing act of juggling commitments, including the caregiving obligations that many Black female academics frequently encounter. The women discuss how gender stereotypes in society lay a burden of caregiving and home duties on them. Their ability to participate as fully as they would like in research and community service projects is limited by this imbalance. Issues with university regulations that lack support structures, like on-campus daycare and flexible work schedules that allow employees to successfully combine personal responsibilities, have been brought to light by studies and study findings. Because of the competing expectations they encounter, women academics are more burdened by these difficulties and frequently feel overburdened and undervalued. This finding highlights how crucial it is to put in place institutional frameworks that support work-life balance and deal with ingrained gender prejudices (Bhengu & Ngcobo, 2022).

Marginalization of Gender Studies and Feminist Research

The findings revealed that women's studies and gender-focused research programs in universities faced marginalization. In comparison to the academic fields that are dominated by males, female academics voiced anger over the idea that their efforts to advance social justice and gender equity were frequently seen as significant.

The marginalization outlined here is consistent with a trend in education where feminist studies and gender are often underfunded and undervalued. There are differences in the distribution of funding, according to the documents reviewed for this study; organizations frequently support and recognize projects and research headed by women. In addition to diminishing the influence of Black female scholars, this systemic undervaluation serves to further exclude minority voices from intellectual discourse (Potgieter & Moleko, 2023).

Institutional Barriers

The study identified challenges in institutions, including the institutional climate, unequal resource distribution, and limited availability of mentorship programs. The majority of participants underlined that the lack of women in high-

ranking academic positions made these challenges worse by preventing them from participating in decision-making processes and from obtaining mentors in the academic community.

While many programs fail to provide significant support for Black women in reality, university reports and official documents emphasized shortcomings in advancing diversity and inclusion efforts for Black women in academia. Involved stakeholders such as University Management Committees (ManCom) called for modifications to university policies and procedures, such as the establishment of mentorship programs, the division of job tasks, and the inclusion of the intersectionality idea.

Resilience and Collective urgency for Black Female academics

Black women academics' strength and teamwork in academia was one important theme that emerged from the study. Findings from studies showed how important it is to form partnerships and connections in order to help one another get over challenges. To help female scholars increase their visibility in academic circles, these collaborations were described as venues for information sharing, mutual support, and advocacy.

This finding agrees with the discussions regarding the role solidarity plays in resolving challenges of institutional exclusion. In addition to challenging established norms, Black female scholars are breaking down barriers and creating cooperative, supportive cultures that will pave the way for future generations of scholars to succeed in a more diversified academic environment (Warren & Bordoloi, 2023).

Engaged scholarship as a tool for Social Change

The research findings also highlighted the resilience and empowerment of South African women academics who are experts at employing engaged scholarship to promote social change, despite the system's challenges. Older academics revealed a strong commitment to community-based research that elevates the voices of underrepresented groups and marginalized people, including women in rural areas.

Through addressing issues and challenging unfair practices in today's higher education institutions, engaged academic work has evolved into a means for Black women scholars to bridge the gap between academia and the community. Examples of

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successful Black female scholars leading research investigations, policy change campaigns, and outreach educational programs were explored in this field of study and documented in these publications. Their efforts did not contribute to community empowerment. changed the role of academics in advancing equality and justice as well (Fataar & Bitzer, 2019).

CONCLUSIONS

This study explores the challenges and opportunities Black female academics face at South African university in Engaged Scholarship. Based on a review of available data and institutional records, the findings show the discrepancies are influenced by factors such as gender, race, class, and other personal traits. The challenges emerged as the need to balance work and caregiving obligations and institutional barriers.

Despite these challenges, the study highlights the resilience and tenacity of women in academia as well as their innovative approaches to problem-solving. These experienced academics now use engaged scholarship as a way to challenge unjust academic standards and improve society. In addition to advancing knowledge, community-based research and change advocacy help to create important advancements that benefit marginalized communities and transform how higher education institutions may confront social injustices.

By presenting the perspectives and experiences of Black female academics as important contributors to diverse viewpoints and combating enduring inequalities that obstruct advancements in this field, this research contributes to the conversations surrounding fairness and diversity in colleges and universities with an emphasis on inclusivity and change in educational institutions. Future research must build on these findings by assessing the effects of specific initiatives aimed at supporting scholars and exploring how research participation can be better leveraged as a tool to impact institutional and social change.

RECOMMENDATIONS

The following strategies are suggested by the study to establish an inclusive academic environment for Black women scholars in South Africa:

- To increase the significance and legitimacy of research on gender issues, universities and colleges should try to incorporate gender perspectives into their fields of study. This can be achieved by integrating gender studies and factors into other areas, promoting interdisciplinary collaboration, and providing funding to support research projects headed by women. By doing this, educational institutions will continue to support gender-focused work and maintain its recognition as a crucial component of improving society.
- To overcome the challenges that Black women academics encounter at the nexus of their identities

and experiences in academic contexts, support networks and mentorship are important. Universities must establish mentorship programs that pair faculty members with mentors in order to address this issue successfully. Support networks among coworkers can also be established by promoting peer-to-peer mentoring. Scholars can be empowered and their possibilities for professional development can be improved by providing workshops centered on leadership development grant writing techniques and sharing research findings.

- Prioritizing the recognition and advancement of gender-focused research and activities spearheaded by women is essential for raising awareness and garnering institutional support. Institutions ought to set up prizes. Funding possibilities should be restricted to gender-focused research, and public presentations, conferences, and institutional publications should emphasize the contributions of female scientists. Universities may validate gender studies and feminist research and encourage wider public involvement in advancing social justice and gender equality by integrating these fields of study into the design of their institutions.
- To effectively address marginalization, institutions must prioritize the development of institutional cultures. This entails conducting diversity assessments, educating employees on how to overcome prejudices, and creating avenues for Black female academics to participate in decision-making. Acting will contribute to ensuring that Black female scholars feel valued and empowered in their environments.
- Universities should make it a priority to advance community-focused scholarship as a component of their academic programs by creating policies for evaluating, supporting, and rewarding scholars who participate in community empowerment efforts. Emphasizing the value of scholarship in success policies that prioritize social justice, equity, and inclusivity will strengthen the innovative work of Black female scholars and increase the practical impact of research. These wide-ranging adjustments are essential to creating an atmosphere that reflects equity, inclusivity, and social advancement.

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